

In Vitro Antagonism of *Trichoderma harzianum* SDM1 Against *Sclerotium rolfii* Associated with Stem Rot Disease of Groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.)

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ABSTRACT

Sclerotium rolfii is one a destructive soil borne fungal pathogen infecting about more than 500 plant species worldwide including groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.). Groundnut is an important oil seed crop in the world. The antagonistic potential of *Trichoderma* species which has been long known to control various soil-borne fungal pathogens in biological way may be utilized. The faster growth rates with which it competes with fungal pathogen mainly brings upon their antagonistic characteristics. An investigation was carried out in laboratory condition towards biological efficacy of *Trichoderma harzianum* SDM1 on potato dextrose agar (PDA) medium for the bio-control of soil borne plant pathogen *Sclerotium rolfii* in-vitro condition. The dual culture technique was followed in which *T. harzianum* SDM1 showed significant antifungal activities towards the pathogen. In Vitro, *T. harzianum* SDM1 significantly inhibited the mycelial radial growth of *S. rolfii* by 64.44±2.2%. The results showed mycelial growth rate for fungal isolate which was determined after 7 days of incubation. Thus, *T. harzianum* showed encouraging results regarding their biocontrol potential against plant pathogen which may be endorsed to substitute harmful chemical supplements that exists in modern day agricultural practices.

Keywords: Groundnut, *Sclerotium rolfii*, Dual Culture, Biocontrol, and *Trichoderma*

INTRODUCTION

Groundnut is considered as one of the most important crops in the world. Groundnut is the 4th most important source of edible oil and is ranked as 3rd most important source of vegetable protein in the world (Smith, 2002). It is cultivated in more than 100 countries of the world. That's why it is referred as a "Universal Crop". Groundnut crop is prone to attack by many diseases and to a much larger extent than many other crops. More than 100 pathogens, including viruses, have been reported to affect groundnut at different stages of growth but only a few are economically important in India such as leaf-spots (Tikka), Early leaf-spot (*Cercospora arachidicola*), Late leaf-spot (*C. personatum*), rust (*P.*

arachidis), and aflatoxin contamination (*Aspergillus flavus* and *A. parasiticus*). The other diseases such as Collar rot (*A. niger*), Stem-rot (*S. rolfsii*), Root-rot (*M. phaseolina*), Bud necrosis (tomato spotted wilt virus), Clump and Peanut (groundnut) mottle disease are localized (Subrahmanyam et al., 1980).

Sclerotium rolfsii (Sacc.) is considered to be disastrous against several crops worldwide with an extensive host range, which includes more than 500 species in 100 families worldwide (Agrios, 2005; Cilliers et al., 2000). The pathogen *S. rolfsii* may cause damping-off or stem rot on host plant with the help of sclerotial germination, which may measure 1-3 mm with mustard-like appearance formed on surfaces of the affected plant parts (Koike, 2004). The pathogen may exploit host plant internally as well as externally for their growth with white cottony-like mycelium formation. Once this fungus begins to exhibit symptoms in the soil, eradication is extremely challenging, even with chemical fungicides. Furthermore, the use of chemicals may be both ineffective and economically burdensome for growers. The control of fungal diseases of plants by the use of naturally occurring antagonistic micro-organisms has been the focus of intense research throughout the world. This approach is popularly known as biological control of plant pathogens. Biological control is a bio-based, ecofriendly strategy that offers a practical and economical alternative for the management of plant pathogens with a potential to emerge as an alternative to chemical control (Mark et al., 2006).

Amongst various biological antagonists like *Bacillus spp.* (Rakh et al., 2015) and *Pseudomonas spp.* (Dalvi & Rakh, 2017), *Trichoderma* species since long have been

extensively used and investigated for their biocontrol ability as they suppress pathogens by various mechanism such as competition (Baker and Cook, 1974; Harman et al., 2004; Reino et al., 2008). Henis et al. (1982) reported mycoparasitism of *Trichoderma spp.* against *Sclerotium rolfsii*, where chlamydospores were abundantly produced in contrast to conidia within the infected fungal sclerotia. Among *Trichoderma* species as fungal antagonists, *Trichoderma harzianum* is considered to be one of the important antagonists that are being considered to eradicate widest range pathogens biologically. Thus, appropriate formulation of fungal antagonist seems to be an alternative way to decrease burden of excessive and harmful use of chemical pesticides. Hence, the present study was undertaken to investigate biocontrol efficacy of *T. harzianum* in in-vitro condition against pathogen *S. rolfsii* by dual culture technique.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Collection of Diseased Groundnut Stem:

Diseased groundnut stems were collected from Pangara fields near the Purna in polyethylene bags and brought to laboratory, Department of Botany, Shri Guru Buddhiswami Mahavidyalaya, Purna (Jn.) Parbhani (Maharashtra) (Photo Plate 1).

Isolation of Phytopathogen:

Diseased groundnut stem showing typical symptoms of stem rot i.e. wilting of total plants, white mycelial growth at collar region of plant (Photo Plate 1) were selected and used as source for the isolation of causative agent. Infected portion of stem was cut into small pieces with sterilized scalpel, cleaned with

Photo plate 1. Disease symptoms on groundnut caused by *Sclerotium rolfsii*.

- A- yellow leaves and wilting; B- mycelium and sclerotia on infected tissue; C- stem rot symptoms; D- peg and pod rot.

distilled water, then surface sterilized with 0.1% HgCl₂ solution for 30 second and again washed thrice with sterile distilled water. Small 1 to 2 pieces were transferred aseptically on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) plates containing Chloramphenicol (30 mg/100 ml) with the help of sterilized forceps under aseptic condition (Rakh, 2010). Inoculated Petri plates were incubated at 25°C for 7 days for growth of the pathogen.

Isolation of Antagonistic Fungi :

The isolation of fungi from rhizospheric soil was carried out in order to search for effective biocontrol agents. The serial dilution plating method was used to dilute the soil sample as described by (Waksman, 1922) with the purpose of minimizing the fungi in the soil in each dilution. The dilution of soil sample was conducted in two replicate where each replicate was diluted six times and labelled as 10⁻¹ until 10⁻⁶. 50 g of soil was added in 100 mL 85% NaCl solution and was thoroughly shaken to mix the solution. The solution then was diluted to a series of prepared vials containing 9 mL 85% NaCl solution. 9 mL of the soil-NaCl solution was transferred to the first vial by using a sterile pipette. Subsequently, another 9 mL of the solution from the first vials was transferred to the second vial and the steps continued until the last vial. 0.1 mL of the solution in each vial was pipetted into the prepared PDA plate. The solution was then spread on the plate by using a hockey stick and incubated at room temperature for seven days. The colony of fungi that appeared in the plate after incubation was then isolated in a new plate. A pure culture of each colony type on each plate was obtained and maintained. The maintenance was done by sub-culturing each of the different colonies onto another new PDA plate. Each colony were cut into 3 mm pieces with a sterilized razor blade, surface sterilized in 70 % ethanol. The colonies were incubated again at room temperature for five days. Each plate of single fungi colony was then sent to Biokart India Pvt. Ltd. for identification purposes.

In Vitro Dual Culture Assay:

20 ml of sterilized PDA was plated in 9 cm petri plates and allowed to solidify. Mycelial discs of 5mm diameter of the antagonists as well as the test pathogen were cut with sterile cork borer from the periphery of an actively growing seven days old culture and then placed on opposite sides of petri plate. The distance between inoculums blocks was

7cm. The inoculated petri plates were incubated at 28±2⁰ C for days. The petri plates isolated with pathogen alone served as control. Three replications were maintained per treatment. The percent reduction in radial growth and sclerotial population of the test pathogen was calculated by using the following formula.

$$I = R1 - R2 / R1 \times 100$$

Where,

R1= Radial growth of *Sclerotium* colony in control plate.

R2= Radial growth of *Sclerotium* colony in dual culture plate

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Isolation of Phytopathogen:

After 7 days incubation on PDA plates, the fungus produced abundant white septate mycelia, 1.5–3.0 μm diameter with clamp connections at each septation, aerial hyphae and also numerous spherical, or ellipsoidal, white sclerotia, 0.5–2.0 mm diameter, which turned brown on maturation, (Photo Plate 2). Based on morphological and culture characteristic, and molecular identification the disease-causing organism was identified as *Sclerotium rolfsii* (Figure 1.0) (Mesquita *et al.*, 2007).

Photo Plate 2: Isolation of *Sclerotium rolfsii* from Infected Groundnut Stem

Isolation of Antagonistic Fungi:

In the current research, a species of *Trichoderma* was isolated, exhibiting colony that was typically fast-

growing with a dense, cottony or woolly aerial mycelium predominantly green due to abundant conidia. The colony coloration ranges from greenish to dark green. The hyaline (transparent) mycelium is highly branched and often displays a floccose (woolly) texture. The conidiophores are branched and bear chains of conidia, which generally exhibit an irregular or verticillate branching pattern. The conidia are characteristically small, smooth, spherical to ellipsoidal, and greenish in color, commonly forming in compact clusters (Siddiquee, 2017; Chen et al., 2025). From these morphological characteristics, the fungal spp. was identified as *Trichoderma spp.* while molecular identification was conducted by Biokart India Private limited, Bengaluru as *Trichoderma harzianum* SDM1 (Figure 2.0).

In Vitro Dual Culture Assay:

The antifungal activity of *T. harzianum* was evaluated by examining its effect on the radial growth rate of the pathogen *S. rolf sii*. This was measured using a dual culture method. *Trichoderma harzianum* reduced the radial growth of *S. rolf sii* by 64.44±2.2% (Table 1.0), as indicated in photo plate 3. The data indicates that *Trichoderma harzianum* significantly inhibited the growth of *S. rolf sii*. Elad et al., (1980) demonstrated that, in culture, *T. harzianum* exhibited superior growth compared to *S. rolf sii*, successfully invading its mycelium even under conditions unfavourable to the pathogen, such as elevated pentachloronitrobenzene concentrations, increased pH levels, or reduced temperatures.

Figure 1: Phylogenetic Alignment of *Sclerotium rolf sii*

Figure 2: Phylogenetic alignment of *Trichoderma harzianum* SDM1

Table 1. Antagonistic effect of *Trichoderma harzianum* SDM1 against growth of *Sclerotium rolf sii* (Dual Culture Technique)

Sr. No.	Treatment	Medium	Radial growth of <i>S. rolf sii</i> in dual culture plate(R2) (cm)	Radial growth of <i>S. rolf sii</i> in control plate(R1) (cm)	Inhibition (%)
1	Sr.+Th1	PDA	3.2±0.2	9±0.0	64.44±2.22

Th = *Trichoderma harzianum*; Sr = *Sclerotium rolf sii*; PDA = Potato dextrose agar

Photo Plate 3: Antagonistic effect of *Trichoderma harzianum* SDM1 against growth of *Sclerotium rolfsii* (Dual Culture Technique)

Barakat *et al.*, (2006) evaluated the antagonistic potential of local microbial isolates against the phytopathogen *Sclerotium rolfsii* using dual culture assays and bioassays on bean plants. Application of the test isolates as a conidial suspension (3×10^6 conidia mL^{-1}) significantly reduced the disease index of bean plants, achieving up to a 67% reduction. The study demonstrated that variations in antagonistic efficacy among isolates were associated with differences in mycelial coiling ability, sporulation capacity, production of fungitoxic metabolites, induction of plant growth responses, and temperature tolerance. Among the isolates tested, Jn14 and T36 exhibited the highest antagonistic activity at 25 °C, inhibiting the mycelial growth of *S. rolfsii* by 79%, primarily due to the production of fungitoxic metabolites.

A study conducted by Kumar *et al.*, (2012) involved isolating five strains of *Trichoderma harzianum* from two different soil types in India. Two isolates were collected from alfisol soils in mango and litchi orchards at the ICAR RCER Research Centre in Plandu, Ranchi, Jharkhand, while three isolates were obtained from inceptisol soils in Varanasi, Eastern Uttar Pradesh, using *Trichoderma* Selective Medium (TSM). The isolates from both soil types—Th-4 and Th-5 from alfisols, and Th-1, Th-2, and Th-3 from inceptisols—were assessed for antagonistic activity against two phytopathogenic sclerotial fungi, *Rhizoctonia solani* and *Sclerotium rolfsii*, via dual culture assays. The alfisol isolates inhibited *R. solani* by 46.77% and 50.34%, while the inceptisol isolates showed inhibition rates of 22.33%, 26.21%, and 23.08%.

Similarly, with *S. rolfsii*, inhibition rates for the alfisol isolates were 44.67% and 47.88%, whereas the inceptisol isolates recorded values of 3.97%, 7.97%, and 28.72%.

Liu *et al.*, (2025) screened various *Trichoderma* species for their mycoparasitic activity against the sclerotia of *Sclerotium rolfsii*. Dual culture assays revealed that isolates FJ002, FJ059, and NM082 exhibited strong inhibitory effects on *S. rolfsii*, with inhibition rates of 100%, 100%, and 86%, respectively, which were significantly higher than those of the other tested strains. Vamshi *et al.*, (2025) reported that *Trichoderma viride* and *Bacillus cereus* exhibited the highest antagonistic activity against *Sclerotium rolfsii*. In dual culture assays, *T. viride* and *B. cereus* inhibited the mycelial growth of *S. rolfsii* by 65.33% and 58.22%, respectively. Similarly, in metabolite assays, *T. viride* and *B. cereus* caused 63.33% and 55.40% inhibition of *S. rolfsii*, indicating the involvement of both direct antagonism and metabolite-mediated suppression.

The present study demonstrated that *Sclerotium rolfsii* was inhibited by 64.44% by *Trichoderma harzianum*. This level of inhibition is considerably higher than that reported by Kumar *et al.*, (2012), where alfisol isolates exhibited inhibition rates of 44.67% and 47.88%, and inceptisol isolates showed markedly lower inhibition ranging from 3.97% to 28.72%. However, the inhibitory effect observed in the present investigation was comparatively lower than the inhibition levels reported by Elad *et al.*, (1980), Liu *et al.*, (2025), and Vamshi *et al.*, (2025).

CONCLUSION

The present investigation successfully achieved the isolation, identification, and in vitro evaluation of the phytopathogen *Sclerotium rolfsii* and its fungal antagonist *Trichoderma harzianum* SDM1. The pathogen isolated from infected groundnut stems exhibited characteristic morphological features such as white septate mycelia with clamp connections and the formation of spherical to ellipsoidal sclerotia that turned brown upon maturation. These cultural and morphological traits, supported by molecular and phylogenetic analysis, confirmed the identity of the pathogen as *Sclerotium rolfsii*.

An antagonistic fungus belonging to the genus *Trichoderma* was also successfully isolated and identified. Based on its fast-growing green colonies, branched conidiophores, and abundant conidia, the isolate was preliminarily identified as *Trichoderma* spp. Molecular characterization further confirmed it as *Trichoderma harzianum* SDM1.

The in vitro dual culture assay clearly demonstrated the antagonistic potential of *T. harzianum* SDM1 against *S. rolfsii*, resulting in a significant inhibition of radial growth ($64.44 \pm 2.22\%$). This inhibition level was higher than several previously reported isolates, particularly those studied by Kumar *et al.*, (2012), though comparatively lower than the exceptionally high inhibition rates reported by Elad *et al.*, (1980), Liu *et al.*, (2025), and Vamshi *et al.*, (2025). The observed suppression of pathogen growth highlights the strong competitive and antagonistic ability of *T. harzianum*, likely mediated through rapid colonization, mycoparasitism, and the production of antifungal metabolites.

Overall, the findings of this findings indicate that *Trichoderma harzianum* SDM1 is an effective antagonist against *Sclerotium rolfsii* under in vitro conditions and holds promise as a potential biocontrol agent for the management of stem rot disease of groundnut. Further studies under greenhouse and field conditions are recommended to validate its efficacy and practical applicability in sustainable disease management strategies

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

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